

Palladium Catalysed Reduction of Chromium Trioxide by Hydrogen**

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Manuscript received 24 April 1978 ; accepted 27 July 1978

The hydrogen reduction of chromium trioxide mechanically mixed with silica supported palladium has been investigated by differential thermal analysis and by thermogravimetry. An oxide intermediate between chromium dioxide and chromium trioxide having overall composition close to Cr_2O_5 has been identified at about 220° . An attempt has been made to characterise this and other products by esr and X-ray diffraction. The process of the catalysed reduction has been discussed.

VARIOUS oxides of chromium between +6 and +3 oxidation states have been the subject of investigation by a number of research workers. Besides the most familiar oxides, such as chromium trioxide, CrO_3 , chromium dioxide, CrO_2 , chromic oxide, Cr_2O_3 , and chromous oxide, CrO , there are other oxides, e.g., Cr_3O_8 , Cr_3O_5 and several non-stoichiometric oxides which are frequently reported in the literature¹⁻⁷.

In recent years Kubota⁸ followed the thermal decomposition of CrO_3 by DTA and TG and claimed to have isolated and characterized Cr_3O_8 and Cr_2O_5 , whereas Lorthioir, et al⁹ reported two intermediate oxides of composition $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{5.33}$ in the temperature range from 288° - 332° and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{4.87}$ from 385° - 416° and concluded that Cr_2O_5 was not formed during the process of decomposition. More recently the decomposition of CrO_3 in hydrogen was studied by Fenerty¹⁰ and a vigorous exothermic reaction at about 350° reported. It was established that in a stream of hydrogen, CrO_3 reduced to Cr_2O_3 at 310° in 4 hours.

The presence of Cr(V) in the activated CrO_3 supported catalysts has been well established¹¹⁻¹⁴ and the catalytic activities of these catalysts have been widely studied¹⁵⁻¹⁷ De Loménie, et al¹⁸ heated a mixture of Al_2O_3 and CrO_3 in the temperature range from 300° - 600° in oxygen and claimed that the isolated product contained Cr(IV) and Cr(V) only. An extremely useful application of this catalyst is to obtain combustion without flame.

In view of numerous applications of a mixture of Cr(IV) and Cr(V), a novel approach has been

made to the problem of identifying chromium oxides intermediate between CrO_3 and Cr_2O_3 . The present article deals with the hydrogen reduction of CrO_3 admixed with silica supported palladium catalyst. The catalysed reduction has two especial advantages over uncatalysed ones. Firstly the reduced oxides are finely divided and have large surface area as they are formed comparatively at lower temperature where the chances of sintering is considerably reduced. Secondly under mild conditions of catalysed reduction new lower oxides may be formed which are otherwise unstable under hard conditions of non-catalytic reduction.

Experimental

Materials and Methods

Palladium (5% Pd w/w) on silica (Davison 70) was deposited by impregnating the support with a solution of PdCl_2 in HCl followed by reduction with hydrogen at 100° . CrO_3 (AR) and CrO_2 (EP) were dried at 120° prior to their use. The samples were prepared by grinding the oxide and the catalyst with an agate pestle and mortar just before use. Accurately weighed quantities of the same mixture were used for all DTA and TG experiments.

DTA measurements were performed on a Stanton Standata apparatus, model 6-25. TG experiments were carried out on a Beckman Vacuum Microbalance, model LM 600 and X-ray diffraction measurements were studied on a Philips unit. The details of these procedures have already been described in a recent publication¹⁹.

** Presented at the National Symposium on Catalysis held at IIT, Kharagpur from Dec. 29-31, 1975.

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ESR measurements were carried out with a Varian E-3 (X-Band) Spectrometer working at microwave frequency of 9.5 GHz. A constant microwave power of 20 mW and modulation amplitude of 0.20 G were used for all samples placed in high grade quartz tubes (160 mm long and 3 mm diameter) and the spectra recorded at 100 KHz modulation frequency. For the determination of g-factor, DPPH ($g : 2.0036$) was used as a standard. In order to allow for the influence of catalysts present in various samples, additional runs were performed on these under identical conditions.

The reduction temperature of various oxides and the mechanical mixtures reported in the present investigation refers either to a maximum or to a minimum. The temperature corrections have been made with the DTA runs of AR grade NH_4NO_3 , KNO_3 and K_2SO_4 performed in air while maintaining other conditions identical to that of the samples.

Results and Discussion

Theoretical weight losses

The theoretical weight losses for the processes discussed below are as follows :

- CrO_3 to Cr_2O_3 , 5.33%
- CrO_3 to Cr_2O_5 , 8.0%
- CrO_3 to CrO_2 , 16.0%
- CrO_3 to Cr_2O_3 , 24.0%

Differential thermal analysis

The DTA curve of pure CrO_3 is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. DTA curve for hydrogen reduction of CrO_3 . In this and latter figures, reduction was continued isothermally at the temperature indicated by the arrow.

When pure CrO_3 is subjected to DTA in hydrogen, a thermogram consisting of four peaks is recorded. The sharp endotherm at 198° is due to melting of CrO_3 . The two exotherms at about 340° and 365° are most probably due to reduction of CrO_3 to intermediate oxides which in presence of hydrogen undergo exothermic reaction to yield Cr_2O_3 and the corresponding peak appears at 390° .

DTA curves of the mechanical mixture containing CrO_3 (83.19%) and 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.8%) are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The thermogram in Fig. 2

Fig. 2. DTA curve for hydrogen reduction of mixture of CrO_3 (83.19%) and 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.80%).

Fig. 3. DTA curve for hydrogen reduction of mixture of CrO_3 (83.19%) and 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.80%) Heating rate above $200^\circ : 3^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$.

was recorded at the heating rate of $10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$. There are four sharp peaks at 176° , 198° , 230° and 315° . The exotherm at 176° indicates that in presence of a catalyst the reduction of CrO_3 commences relatively at lower temperature. However, before the process is complete, the unreduced CrO_3 melts which is apparent from the endotherm at 198° followed by an exotherm at 230° . From the thermogram in Fig. 2 it appears that had there been no free CrO_3 at 176° the two peaks at 176° and 230° would have appeared as a single exotherm in this range. In order to resolve the shoulder at 296° (cf. Fig. 2) the above experiment was repeated at the heating rate of $10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$ till the temperature reached 200° and afterwards the thermogram was recorded at the heating rate of 3° min^{-1} . The thermogram is shown in Fig. 3. As expected there was no change in the position of peaks at 176° and 198° but the peaks at 230° and 315° (cf. Fig. 2) appeared at 215° and 265° respectively. The shoulder at 296° in Fig. 2 was recorded as a well defined peak at 235° .

DTA curves of CrO_3 and of a mixture of CrO_3 (83.19%) and 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.8%) in hydrogen are shown in Fig. 6. With CrO_3 alone the reduction commences at about 200° and an exotherm occurs at 310° whereas the catalysed reduction starts at 180° and a sharp maximum appears at 255° . The product is yellowish green in colour. From the two curves shown in Fig. 6, it is evident that catalysed reduction of CrO_3 to CrOOH is much faster and the process is complete at relatively lower temperature.

Thermogravimetric analysis

The TG curve of a mechanical mixture containing CrO_3 (83.2%) and 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.8%) in 400 Torr hydrogen is shown in Fig. 4. It is interesting to observe that a loss in weight due to reduction of

Fig. 4. TG curve for hydrogen reduction of mixture of CrO_3 (83.19%) and 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.80%).

CrO_3 commences at about 50° . This is entirely different from the palladium catalysed reduction of MoO_3 ¹⁹ where there is a gain in weight due to formation of hydrogen molybdenum bronze. The rate of weight loss is considerably increased at about 170° followed by a break at the melting temperature of CrO_3 . However, the reduction proceeds smoothly and from a weight loss of 7.5% recorded at 240° , it appears that the overall composition at this temperature approximating to Cr_2O_5 . A small weight loss in the temperature range from 240° to 280° indicates a slow process of reduction. Just above 280° there is an abrupt weight loss of about 8%, which corresponds to the formation of CrO_2 , followed by a gradual loss in weight on further heating at 500° approaching to 24% indicates that the end product is Cr_2O_3 . It is very likely that the intermediate compound CrOOH was also formed during the process of reduction. The interconversion of orthorhombic chromium oxo-hydroxide and chromium dioxide at 330° has recently been investigated by Alario Franco and Sing²⁰ and we have also obtained similar results.

X-ray Diffraction and Electron Spin Resonance

The powder photograph of the mechanical mixture reduced in hydrogen at 215° for about 20 mins. shows a diffused band and a few very weak lines which are also found in the powder photograph of Cr_3O_8 ²¹. A complete absence of characteristic lines of CrO_3 and CrO_2 on the X-ray pattern suggests that there is formation of a new oxide approximating to Cr_2O_5 . This is further supported by a complete absence of ferromagnetic materials in the product examined by ESR. Debyograms of the reduced products obtained at 180° and at 350° show the characteristic lines of CrO_3 and Cr_2O_3 respectively.

ESR spectrum of the product reduced at 215° for 20 mins. when diluted 9 times with SiO_2 shows a broad asymmetric signal with g-factor 1.97 (cf. Fig. 5) whereas γ -phase chromium oxide reported by Cossee and van Reijen²¹, Poole et al²² shows a sharp absorption peak characterized by a g-factor of 1.969 and a line width of about 40-50 gauss. It appears that comparatively broad signal may partly be due to clumps and clusters of Cr(V) which are badly dispersed, and partly due to relaxation effects. Although slight asymmetry is expected with such compounds, in the present case it has been enhanced due to presence of the catalyst as shown by the dotted line in Fig. 5.

Conclusion :

The reduction temperature of CrO_3 is considerably influenced by Pd/SiO_2 . In the absence of a catalyst, the reduction does not commence below 250° whereas the catalysed reduction of CrO_3 starts at 50° . Unlike MoO_3 and WO_3 , CrO_3 does not form bronze. By careful control of the experimental conditions, it is possible to isolate new oxides of chromium which may be catalytically more effective.

Fig. 5. ESR spectrum of hydrogen reduction of mixture of CrO_2 (83.19%) and 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.80%) at 215° for 20 mins., and diluted 9 times with SiO_2 . Cr: 4.8% (wt).

Fig. 6. DTA curves for hydrogen reduction of mixture of $\text{CrO}_2 + \text{Pd/SiO}_2$ and for CrO_2 . I(a) CrO_2 and II(b) CrO_2 (83.19%) + 5% Pd/SiO_2 (16.80%).

Acknowledgement

Dr. J. B. P. Tripathi is indebted to Brunel University for a Research Fellowship, during the tenure of which part of this work was performed. The authors are also grateful to Dr. K. A. K. Lott for helpful discussion.

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